

Ordinary substitution corresponds to de Bruijn substitution

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1 Introduction

When presenting Kripke models, almost no one checks the quantifier rules (see [4] as a rare exception, feel how difficult it is). Let's briefly describe the essence of the problem. Let a set of types $A, B, C \dots$ be given and each type is associated with an object of some category \mathbf{C} (in the simplest case it is the category of sets). Each term is associated with a certain arrow of category \mathbf{C} . For example, if $x : nat, y : nat$, then $x + y : nat$, which is written as follows

$$x : nat, y : nat \vdash x + y : nat$$

and the corresponding arrow looks like this

$$nat \times nat \xrightarrow{+} nat$$

For detailed description see [6]. What does substitution correspond to? For example, consider the term $[x/y](x + y)$

$$[x/y](x + y) = x + x$$

so the corresponding arrow looks like this

$$x : nat \vdash [x/y](x + y) : nat$$

$$x : nat \vdash x + x : nat$$

$$nat \xrightarrow{+\circ(id,id)} nat$$

More generally, let N and M be terms such that

$$x : A \vdash N : B$$

$$x : A, y : B \vdash M : C$$

and the corresponding arrows look like this

$$A \xrightarrow{N} B$$

$$A \times B \xrightarrow{M} C$$

We believe that there should be

$$x : A \vdash [N/y] M : C$$

and the corresponding arrow should look like this

$$A \xrightarrow{M \circ \langle id, N \rangle} C$$

We believe that this is also true for lambda calculus, in which both M and N can contain binders (and the definition of substitution becomes complicated). There is no published proof as far as I know. It is typical that Lambek and Scott in [6] do not mention this problem at all.

The plan of the article is as follows. In Section 2 we prove a “lightweight version” of the main theorem. It is not needed for the main result, but it helps to understand the scheme of the proof. In Section 3 we prove the main theorem. In Section 4 we look at the formalization of the main theorem with Coq. Instead of category-theoretic notations, we will use more appropriate notations related to de Bruijn terms ([1],[2]).

Tab. 1: Typing rules

$\Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A$	(axiom)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash x : A}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash x : A} \quad (y \neq x)$	(weakening)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M : A \rightarrow B \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash MN : B}$	(app)
$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : B}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x^A M : A \rightarrow B}$	(lam)

2 Lightweight version

Definition 2.1. Types are built from atomic types using arrow $A \rightarrow B$. We will denote types by letters A, B, C, D, T .

Let Var be a set (of variables) with decidable equality and a function $fresh : P_{fin}(Var) \rightarrow Var$ such that $fresh(S) \notin S$ for each finite set $S \subseteq Var$. Let x, y, z range over Var . Lambda-terms are built from variables using application MN and abstraction $\lambda x^A M$. We will denote lambda-terms by letters M, N, L .

Contexts are lists of the form $x_1 : A_1, \dots, x_n : A_n$. Variables in a context can be repeated (this is important). We will denote contexts by letters Γ, Δ, Σ .

Definition 2.2. The typing rules shown in Table 1 are taken from [8] (the system \vdash_{lt} of “liberal terms”). They are equivalent to the usual ones, which is not difficult to prove. Their main feature is a very limited weakening rule.

Example 2.3.

$$\frac{x : A, x : B \vdash x : B}{x : A \vdash \lambda x^B x : B \rightarrow B} \quad (lam)$$

$$\frac{x : A \vdash \lambda x^B x : B \rightarrow B}{\vdash \lambda x^A \lambda x^B x : A \rightarrow B \rightarrow B} \quad (lam)$$

Example 2.4. Let $x \neq y$

$$\frac{x : A, y : A \rightarrow B \vdash y : A \rightarrow B \quad \frac{x : A \vdash x : A}{x : A, y : A \rightarrow B \vdash x : A} \text{ (weakening)}}{x : A, y : A \rightarrow B \vdash yx : B} \text{ (app)}$$

Our goal is to prove the admissibility of the following rule

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash [N/x]M : T}$$

Lemma 2.5.

If $\Gamma \vdash x : T$ is provable, then the proof is unique.

If $\Gamma \vdash x : T$ is provable for some T , then T is unique for given Γ and x .

Proof. Induction on the length of Γ .

Case 1. Γ is empty.

There are no rules to prove $\vdash x : T$

Case 2. Γ has the form $\Delta, y : A$

Case 2.1. $y = x$

It must be $T = A$ for $\Delta, x : A \vdash x : T$ to be provable. The unique proof is the axiom

$$\Delta, x : A \vdash x : A$$

Case 2.2. $y \neq x$

Any proof of $\Delta, y : A \vdash x : T$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Delta \vdash x : T \end{array}}{\Delta, y : A \vdash x : T} \text{ (weakening)}$$

Use the induction hypothesis for $\Delta \vdash x : T$

□

Theorem 2.6.

If $\Gamma \vdash M : T$ is provable, then the proof is unique.

If $\Gamma \vdash M : T$ is provable for some T , then T is unique for given Γ and M .

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. Use Lemma 2.5.

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda x^A N$

Any proof of $\Gamma \vdash \lambda x^A N : T$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A \vdash N : B \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x^A N : A \rightarrow B} \quad (lam)$$

where $T = A \rightarrow B$. Use the induction hypothesis for $\Gamma, x : A \vdash N : B$

Case 3. M has the form NL

Any proof of $\Gamma \vdash NL : T$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash N : A \rightarrow T \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash L : A \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash NL : T} \quad (app)$$

Use the induction hypotheses for $\Gamma \vdash N : A \rightarrow T$ and $\Gamma \vdash L : A$ □

Next, we will prove the admissibility of the following rules

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash M : T}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T}{\Gamma \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

Lemma 2.7. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta \vdash z : T}$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash z : T}$$

Case 1.1. $z = x$

It must be $T = B$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash x : B}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash x : B}$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 1.2. $z \neq x$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z : T}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash z : T} \text{ (weakening)}}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash z : T} \text{ (weakening)}$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z : T}}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash z : T} \text{ (weakening)}$$

Case 2. Δ has the form $\Sigma, w : C$ The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $T = C$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}{\Gamma, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \text{ (weakening)}}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}$$

By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \text{ (our rule)}}{\Gamma, x : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \text{ (weakening)}$$

□

Theorem 2.8. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta \vdash M : T}$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. Use Lemma 2.7.

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda y^C N$. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : T}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : T}$$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta, y : C \vdash N : D}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : C \rightarrow D} \text{ (lam)}}{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : C \rightarrow D} \text{ (lam)}$$

where $T = C \rightarrow D$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta, y : C \vdash N : D}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta, y : C \vdash N : D}$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B, \Delta, y : C \vdash N : D}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta, y : C \vdash N : D} \text{ (our rule)}}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : C \rightarrow D} \text{ (lam)}}{\Gamma, x : B, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^C N : C \rightarrow D} \text{ (lam)}$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise. □

Corollary 2.9. *(aka contr) The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash M : T}$$

Lemma 2.10. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Delta \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Case 1.1. $z = x$

It must be $T = A$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash x : A}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash x : A} \quad (x \neq y)$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 1.2. $z = y$

It must be $T = B$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash y : B}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash y : B} \quad (x \neq y)$$

The conclusion is easily provable.

Case 1.3. $z \neq x, z \neq y$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z : T}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})}{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z : T}}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

Case 2. Δ has the form $\Sigma, w : C$ The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $T = C$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C} \quad (x \neq y)$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (\text{our rule})}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

□

Theorem 2.11. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, \Delta \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A, \Delta \vdash M : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. Use Lemma 2.10.

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda z^C N$. Exercise.

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise.

□

Corollary 2.12. (*aka perm*) *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M : T} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Lemma 2.13. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Delta)$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z)$$

This is the weakening rule.

Case 2. Δ has the form $\Sigma, w : C$ The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma \vee z = w)$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $T = C$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z : T \end{array}}{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z : T \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{our rule})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

□

Theorem 2.14. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M) \vee x \in \Delta)$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee x \in \Delta)$$

Use Lemma 2.13 (the side conditions are different, but equal, check this for $x = z$, then for $x \neq z$)

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda y^B N$. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^B N : T}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^B N : T} \quad (x \notin FV(\lambda y^B N) \vee x \in \Delta)$$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C}{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^B N : B \rightarrow C} \quad (lam)$$

where $T = B \rightarrow C$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C} \quad (x \notin FV(N) \vee x \in \Delta \vee x = y)$$

Note that the side condition

$$x \notin FV(N) \vee x \in \Delta \vee x = y$$

is equal to

$$x \notin FV(\lambda y^B N) \vee x \in \Delta$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C} \quad (our\ rule)$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta, y : B \vdash N : C}{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash \lambda y^B N : B \rightarrow C} \quad (lam)$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise. □

Corollary 2.15. (*aka weak*) *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

Lemma 2.16. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Delta)$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash z : T}{\Gamma \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z)$$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash z : T \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

Case 2. Δ has the form $\Sigma, w : C$ The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma \vee z = w)$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $T = C$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash w : C}$$

The conclusion is an axiom.

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Sigma \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \overset{\vdots}{\Sigma} \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z : T} \quad (\text{our rule})}{\Gamma, \Sigma, w : C \vdash z : T} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

□

Theorem 2.17. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash M : T}{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M) \vee x \in \Delta)$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, \Delta \vdash z : T}{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z : T} \quad (x \neq z \vee x \in \Delta)$$

Use Lemma 2.16 (the side conditions are different, but equal, check this for $x = z$, then for $x \neq z$)

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda y^B N$. Exercise.

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise.

□

Corollary 2.18. *(aka strength) The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T}{\Gamma \vdash M : T} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

We will denote substitution as $[N/x]M$.

Definition 2.19. Let $y \neq x$. Define substitution as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
[N/x]x &= N \\
[N/x]y &= y \\
[N/x]\lambda x^A M &= \lambda x^A M \\
[N/x]\lambda y^A M &= \lambda y^A M && (x \notin FV(M)) \\
[N/x]\lambda y^A M &= \lambda y^A [N/x]M && (x \in FV(M), y \notin FV(N)) \\
[N/x]\lambda y^A M &= \lambda z^A [N/x][z/y]M && (x \in FV(M), y \in FV(N)) \\
&&& \text{where } z = \text{fresh}(FV(M) \cup FV(N)) \\
[N/x](ML) &= ([N/x]M)[N/x]L
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.20. $\text{count}(M)$ is the total number of lambdas in M

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{count}(x) &= 0 \\
\text{count}(\lambda x^A M) &= \text{count}(M) + 1 \\
\text{count}(MN) &= \text{count}(M) + \text{count}(N)
\end{aligned}$$

We will believe without proof that substitution is total function and

$$\text{count}([z/y]M) = \text{count}(M)$$

Theorem 2.21. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash M : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash [N/x]M : T}$$

Proof. Induction on $(\text{count}(M), \text{length}(M))$, ordered lexicographically. Suppose the rule is admissible for all M' such that $\text{count}(M') < \text{count}(M)$ or $\text{count}(M') = \text{count}(M) \wedge \text{length}(M') < \text{length}(M)$

Case 1. M is a variable y

Case 1.1. $y = x$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x]x = N$$

and the rule has the following trivial form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash x : A \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash N : A}$$

Case 1.2. $y \neq x$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x]y = y$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash y : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash y : T}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash y : T \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash y : T} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

Case 2. M begins with lambda.

Case 2.1. M has the form $\lambda x^B M'$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda x^B M' = \lambda x^B M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda x^B M' : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x^B M' : T}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash M' : C \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda x^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \quad (\textit{lam})$$

where $T = B \rightarrow C$. We can proof the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, x : B \vdash M' : C \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : B \vdash M' : C} \quad (\textit{2.9 contr})}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \quad (\textit{lam})$$

Case 2.2. M has the form $\lambda y^B M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \notin FV(M')$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y^B M' = \lambda y^B M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y^B M' : T}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \quad (lam)$$

where $T = B \rightarrow C$. We can proof the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C \end{array}}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M' : C} \quad (2.12 \text{ perm})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash M' : C} \quad (2.18 \text{ strength})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y : B \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \quad (lam)$$

Case 2.3. M has the form $\lambda y^B M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \in FV(M')$, $y \notin FV(N)$
The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y^B M' = \lambda y^B [N/x] M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y^B [N/x] M' : T}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C \end{array}}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \quad (lam)$$

where $T = B \rightarrow C$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M' : C \quad \Gamma, y : B \vdash N : A}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash [N/x] M' : C}$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma, y : B, x : A \vdash M' : C} \text{ (2.12 perm)} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash N : A} \text{ (2.15 weak)}}{\Gamma, y : B \vdash [N/x]M' : C} \text{ (our rule)}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y : B \vdash [N/x]M' : C}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y^B [N/x]M' : B \rightarrow C} \text{ (lam)}$$

Case 2.4. M has the form $\lambda y^B M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \in FV(M')$, $y \in FV(N)$
The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y^B M' = \lambda z^B [N/x] [z/y] M'$$

where $z \notin FV(M')$, $z \notin FV(N)$

(note that $z \neq x$ because $x \in FV(M')$ and $z \neq y$ because $y \in FV(N)$)

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : T \quad \Gamma \vdash N : A}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda z^B [N/x] [z/y] M' : T}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma, x : A \vdash \lambda y^B M' : B \rightarrow C} \text{ (lam)}$$

where $T = B \rightarrow C$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rules are admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x : A, z : B, y : B \vdash M' : C \quad \Gamma, x : A, z : B \vdash z : B}{\Gamma, x : A, z : B \vdash [z/y] M' : C} \text{ (1)}$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, z : B, x : A \vdash [z/y] M' : C \quad \Gamma, z : B \vdash N : A}{\Gamma, z : B \vdash [N/x] [z/y] M' : C} \text{ (2)}$$

We can proof the conclusion

$$\begin{array}{c}
\vdots \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, z : B \vdash M' : C} \text{(2.15 weak)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A, y : B, z : B \vdash M' : C}{\Gamma, x : A, z : B, y : B \vdash M' : C} \text{(2.12 perm)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A, z : B \vdash z : B}{\Gamma, x : A, z : B \vdash [z/y]M' : C} \text{(1)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x : A, z : B \vdash [z/y]M' : C}{\Gamma, z : B, x : A \vdash [z/y]M' : C} \text{(2.12 perm)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, z : B \vdash [N/x] [z/y]M' : C}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda z^B [N/x] [z/y]M' : C} \text{(lam)} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash \dot{N} : A}{\Gamma, z : B \vdash N : A} \text{(2.15 weak)} \text{(2)}
\end{array}$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise.

Note that $\text{count}(N)$ may be equal to $\text{count}(NL)$, but $\text{length}(N) < \text{length}(NL)$

□

Tab. 2: Terms

$x, y, z, w ::= x \mid y \mid z \mid \dots$	(Variables)
$M, N ::= x \mid MN \mid \lambda x M$	(Terms)
$M, N ::= \underline{n} \mid MN \mid \lambda M$	(De Bruijn Terms)

3 Main theorem

Definition 3.1. In this chapter, for simplicity, we will consider untyped terms.

Let Var be a set (of variables) with decidable equality and a function $fresh: P_{fin}(Var) \rightarrow Var$ such that $fresh(S) \notin S$ for each finite set $S \subseteq Var$. Let x, y, z range over Var . Lambda-terms are built from variables using application MN and abstraction $\lambda x M$. We will denote lambda-terms by letters M, N, L .

De Bruijn indices have the form \underline{n} , where n is a natural number in some standard notation (for example, $0, s0, s s 0 \dots$ we will use decimal notation)

De Bruijn lambda-terms are built from de Bruijn indices using application MN and abstraction λM (Table 2). We will denote de Bruijn lambda-terms by letters M, N, L .

Contexts are lists of variables x_1, \dots, x_n . Variables in a context can be repeated (this is important). We will denote contexts by letters Γ, Δ, Σ .

Suppose that a context Γ and a term M are given, and all free variables of M are contained in Γ . We can construct the de Bruijn term corresponding to M . It is convenient to denote this operation by an infix operator, for example $\Gamma \vdash M$. Thus, \vdash is a two-place function that produces, given Γ and M , a certain de Bruijn term.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\Gamma, x \vdash x) &= \underline{0} \\
 (\Gamma, y \vdash x) &= \underline{(\Gamma \vdash x) + 1} \quad (y \neq x) \\
 (\Gamma \vdash MN) &= (\Gamma \vdash M)(\Gamma \vdash N) \\
 (\Gamma \vdash \lambda x M) &= \lambda (\Gamma, x \vdash M)
 \end{aligned}$$

Tab. 3: Matching rules

$\Gamma, x \vdash x = \underline{0}$	(axiom)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash x = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, y \vdash x = \underline{n+1}}$	($y \neq x$) (weakening)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash MN = MN}$	(app)
$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash M = M}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x M = \lambda M}$	(lam)

To establish a connection with the previous section, let's write the rules for calculating $\Gamma \vdash M$ in a different way.

Definition 3.2. I will write $\Gamma \vdash M = M$ instead of $(\Gamma \vdash M) = M$. Notation $\Gamma \vdash M = M$ means “ M matches de Bruijn term M in context Γ ” (Table 3).

Example 3.3. Let $x \neq y, x \neq z$

$$\frac{\frac{x \vdash x = \underline{0}}{x, y \vdash x = \underline{1}} \text{ (weakening)}}{x, y, z \vdash x = \underline{2}} \text{ (weakening)}$$

Example 3.4. Let $x \neq y$

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{x \vdash x = \underline{0}}{x, y \vdash x = \underline{1}} \text{ (weakening)} \quad x, y \vdash y = \underline{0}}{x, y \vdash xy = \underline{10}} \text{ (app)}}{x \vdash \lambda y xy = \lambda \underline{10}} \text{ (lam)}$$

Example 3.5.

$$\frac{x, x \vdash x = \underline{0}}{x \vdash \lambda x x = \lambda \underline{0}} \text{ (lam)}$$

$$\frac{x \vdash \lambda x x = \lambda \underline{0}}{\vdash \lambda x \lambda x x = \lambda \lambda \underline{0}} \text{ (lam)}$$

Our goal is to prove the admissibility of the following rule

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash M = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash [N/x]M = M [N/]}$$

Lemma 3.6.

If Γ contains x , then $\Gamma \vdash x = M$ is provable for a unique M , the proof is unique and M is a de Bruijn index.

Proof. Induction on the length of Γ .

Case 1. Γ is empty. The premise is false.

Case 2. Γ has the form Δ, y (and Δ, y contains x)

Case 2.1. $y = x$

It must be $M = \underline{0}$ for $\Delta, x \vdash x = M$ to be provable. The unique proof is the axiom

$$\Delta, x \vdash x = \underline{0}$$

Case 2.2. $y \neq x$

In this case Δ contains x .

Any proof of $\Delta, y \vdash x = M$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Delta \vdash x = \underline{n} \end{array}}{\Delta, y \vdash x = \underline{n+1}} \quad (\textit{weakening})$$

Use the induction hypothesis for Δ and x , put $M = \underline{n+1}$ □

Theorem 3.7.

If Γ contains all free variables of M , then $\Gamma \vdash M = M$ is provable for a unique M and the proof is unique.

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. Use Lemma 3.6.

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda x N$ (and Γ contains all free variables of $\lambda x N$)

Any proof of $\Gamma \vdash \lambda x N = M$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x \vdash N = N \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x N = \lambda N} \quad (\textit{lam})$$

where $M = \lambda N$. Note that Γ, x contains all free variables of N .

Use the induction hypothesis for Γ, x and N

Case 3. M has the form NL

Any proof of $\Gamma \vdash NL = M$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash N = N \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash L = L \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash NL = NL} \quad (app)$$

where $M = NL$. Use the induction hypotheses for $\Gamma \vdash N = N$ and $\Gamma \vdash L = L$. □

Theorem 3.8. *If $\Gamma \vdash M = M$ is provable, then Γ contains all free variables of M .*

Proof. Straightforward induction on the proof. □

Definition 3.9. Let DB be the set of all de Bruijn terms. We define a set of functions (substitutions)

$$S : DB \rightarrow DB$$

as shown in the Table 4.

Strange substitution $\binom{0}{1}$ corresponds to De Bruijn's θ_2 ([3],[7]). The names of the equalities (except Perm 0,1,2) are taken from [2]. The notation is not quite traditional, but uses half as many parentheses and brackets as traditional one. I understand that this will scare off many readers. So we will

1. write substitutions on the left side;

$$S M \text{ instead of } MS$$

2. not put \uparrow and $\uparrow\uparrow$ in brackets;

$$\uparrow M \text{ instead of } M[\uparrow]$$

$$S \uparrow M \text{ instead of } M[\uparrow S]$$

Example 3.10.

$$[N/] M \text{ corresponds to } M[N/]$$

$$[N/] \lambda M \text{ corresponds to } (\lambda M)[N/]$$

$$\lambda [N/] M \text{ corresponds to } \lambda(M[N/])$$

Tab. 4: Substitutions

$S ::= [N/] \uparrow \uparrow \binom{0}{1} \mid S \uparrow$	(Substitutions)
$S(MN) = (SM)(SN)$	(App)
$S \lambda M = \lambda S \uparrow M$	(Lambda)
$[N/] \underline{0} = N$	(FVar)
$[N/] \underline{k+1} = \underline{k}$	(RVar)
$\uparrow \underline{k} = \underline{k+1}$	(VarShift)
$S \uparrow \underline{0} = \underline{0}$	(FVarLift)
$S \uparrow \underline{k+1} = \uparrow S \underline{k}$	(RVarLift)
$\binom{0}{1} \underline{0} = \underline{1}$	(Perm0)
$\binom{0}{1} \underline{1} = \underline{0}$	(Perm1)
$\binom{0}{1} \underline{k+2} = \underline{k+2}$	(Perm2)

$\uparrow \lambda M$ corresponds to $(\lambda M)[\uparrow]$

$\lambda \uparrow M$ corresponds to $\lambda(M[\uparrow])$

$\uparrow \uparrow M$ corresponds to $M[\uparrow \uparrow]$

$[N/] \uparrow M$ corresponds to $M[\uparrow (N/)]$

Example 3.11.

$[1/] \lambda \underline{0} =$

$= \lambda [1/] \uparrow \underline{0}$ (Lambda)

$= \lambda \underline{0}$ (FVarLift)

Definition 3.12.

$$S \uparrow^n \text{ is short for } S \underbrace{\uparrow \dots \uparrow}_n$$

Next, we will prove the admissibility of the following rules

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash M = \binom{0}{1} M} \quad (x \neq y)$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, x \vdash M = \uparrow M} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

Lemma 3.13. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{m}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$\underline{m} = \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{\text{len}} \underline{n} \quad (\text{len} = \text{length}(\Delta))$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash z = \binom{0}{1} \underline{n}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Case 1.1. $z = x$

It must be $n = 1$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash x = \underline{1}}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash x = \binom{0}{1} \underline{1}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Further,

$$\binom{0}{1} \underline{1} = \underline{0} \quad (\text{Perm1})$$

and the conclusion $\Gamma, y, x \vdash x = \underline{0}$ is an axiom.

Case 1.2. $z = y$

It must be $n = 0$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash y = \underline{0}}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash y = \binom{0}{1} \underline{0}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Further,

$$\binom{0}{1} \underline{0} = \underline{1} \quad (\text{Perm0})$$

and the conclusion $\Gamma, y, x \vdash y = \underline{1}$ is easily provable.

Case 1.3. $z \neq x, z \neq y$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z = \underline{k}}{\Gamma, x \vdash z = \underline{k+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})}{\Gamma, x, y \vdash z = \underline{k+2}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\vdots}{\Gamma \vdash z = \underline{k}}{\Gamma, y \vdash z = \underline{k+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash z = \underline{k+2}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

Further,

$$\binom{0}{1} \underline{k+2} = \underline{k+2} \quad (\text{Perm2})$$

Case 2. Δ has the form Σ, w

Let $len = length(\Sigma)$, then $len + 1 = length(\Delta)$

The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{m}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$\underline{m} = \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n}$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $n = 0$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Sigma, w \vdash w = \underline{0}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma, w \vdash w = \underline{0}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

The conclusion is an axiom and

$$\binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{0} = \underline{0} \quad (\text{FVarLift})$$

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k} \end{array}}{\Gamma, x, y, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{k+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

where $n = k + 1$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$\underline{k'} = \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len} \underline{k} \quad (*)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k} \end{array}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}} \quad (\text{our rule})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}}{\Gamma, y, x, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{k'+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

therefore it must be $m = k' + 1$. Further,

$$\underline{m} = \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n}$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n} &= \\ &= \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{k+1} \\ &= \uparrow \binom{0}{1} \uparrow^{len} \underline{k} \quad (\text{RVarLift}) \\ &= \uparrow \underline{k'} \quad (*) \\ &= \underline{k'+1} \quad (\text{VarShift}) \\ &= \underline{m} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.14. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta \vdash M = M'} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{\text{len}} M \quad (\text{len} = \text{length}(\Delta))$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. Use Lemma 3.13.

Case 2. M has the form λzN . The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta \vdash \lambda zN = M}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta \vdash \lambda zN = M'} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{\text{len}} M$$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta, z \vdash N = N}{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta \vdash \lambda zN = \lambda N} \quad (\text{lam})$$

where $M = \lambda N$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta, z \vdash N = N}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta, z \vdash N = N'} \quad (x \neq y)$$

where

$$N' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{\text{len}+1} N \quad (*)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y, \Delta, z \vdash N = N}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta, z \vdash N = N'} \quad (\text{our rule})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta, z \vdash N = N'}{\Gamma, y, x, \Delta \vdash \lambda zN = \lambda N'} \quad (\text{lam})$$

therefore it must be $M' = \lambda N'$. Further,

$$M' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{len} M$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{len} M = \\ & = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{len} \lambda N \\ & = \lambda \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \uparrow^{len+1} N \quad (\text{Lambda}) \\ & = \lambda N' \quad (*) \\ & = M' \end{aligned}$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise. □

Corollary 3.15. (*aka perm*) *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash M = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} M} \quad (x \neq y)$$

Lemma 3.16. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{m}} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Delta)$$

where

$$\underline{m} = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \underline{n} \quad (len = length(\Delta))$$

Proof. Induction on the length of Δ

Case 1. Δ is empty. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, x \vdash z = \uparrow \underline{n}} \quad (x \neq z)$$

This is the weakening rule

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, x \vdash z = \underline{n+1}} \quad (x \neq z)$$

because

$$\uparrow \underline{n} = \underline{n+1} \quad (\text{VarShift})$$

Case 2. Δ has the form Σ, w

Let $len = length(\Sigma)$, then $len + 1 = length(\Delta)$

The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, x, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{m}} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma \vee z = w)$$

where

$$\underline{m} = \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n}$$

Case 2.1. $z = w$

It must be $n = 0$ for the premise to be provable

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma, w \vdash w = \underline{0}}{\Gamma, x, \Sigma, w \vdash w = \underline{0}}$$

The conclusion is an axiom and

$$\uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{0} = \underline{0} \quad (\text{FVarLift})$$

Case 2.2. $z \neq w$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k} \end{array}}{\Gamma, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{k+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

where $n = k + 1$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k}}{\Gamma, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}} \quad (x \neq z \vee z \in \Sigma)$$

where

$$\underline{k'} = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \underline{k} \quad (*)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k} \end{array}}{\Gamma, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}} \quad (\text{our rule})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, \Sigma \vdash z = \underline{k'}}{\Gamma, x, \Sigma, w \vdash z = \underline{k'+1}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

therefore it must be $m = k' + 1$. Further,

$$\underline{m} = \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n}$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{n} &= \\ &= \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \underline{k+1} \\ &= \uparrow \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \underline{k} \quad (\text{RVarLift}) \\ &= \uparrow \underline{k'} \quad (*) \\ &= \underline{k'+1} \quad (\text{VarShift}) \\ &= \underline{m} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.17. *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash M = M'} \quad (x \notin FV(M) \vee x \in \Delta)$$

where

$$M' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} M \quad (len = length(\Delta))$$

Proof. Induction on the structure of M .

Case 1. M is a variable. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash z = \underline{m}} \quad (x \neq z \vee x \in \Delta)$$

where

$$\underline{m} = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \underline{n}$$

Use Lemma 3.16 (the side conditions are different, but equal, check this for $x = z$, then for $x \neq z$)

Case 2. M has the form $\lambda y N$. The rule has the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash \lambda y N = M}{\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash \lambda y N = M'} \quad (x \notin FV(\lambda y N) \vee x \in \Delta)$$

where

$$M' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} M$$

The unique proof of the premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma, \Delta \vdash \lambda y N = \lambda \mathbf{N}} \quad (\text{lam})$$

where $\mathbf{M} = \lambda \mathbf{N}$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma, x, \Delta, y \vdash N = \mathbf{N}'} \quad (x \notin FV(N) \vee x \in \Delta \vee x = y)$$

where

$$\mathbf{N}' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \mathbf{N} \quad (*)$$

Note that the side condition

$$x \notin FV(N) \vee x \in \Delta \vee x = y$$

is equal to

$$x \notin FV(\lambda y N) \vee x \in \Delta$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, \Delta, y \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma, x, \Delta, y \vdash N = \mathbf{N}'} \quad (\text{our rule})}{\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash \lambda y N = \lambda \mathbf{N}'} \quad (\text{lam})$$

therefore it must be $\mathbf{M}' = \lambda \mathbf{N}'$. Further,

$$\mathbf{M}' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \mathbf{M}$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \mathbf{M} &= \\ &= \uparrow \uparrow^{len} \lambda \mathbf{N} \\ &= \lambda \uparrow \uparrow^{len+1} \mathbf{N} \quad (\text{Lambda}) \\ &= \lambda \mathbf{N}' \quad (*) \\ &= \mathbf{M}' \end{aligned}$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise. □

Corollary 3.18. (*aka weak*) *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M = M}{\Gamma, x \vdash M = \uparrow M} \quad (x \notin FV(M))$$

Theorem 3.19. *Suppose*

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma, x, \Delta \vdash M = M' \text{ is provable for some } M' \\ &x \notin FV(M) \vee x \in \Delta \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma, \Delta \vdash M = M \text{ is provable for some } M \text{ and} \\ &M' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} M \quad (len = length(\Delta)) \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The context Γ, x, Δ contains all free variables of M (Theorem 3.8). The context Γ, Δ also contains all free variables of M (because $x \notin FV(M) \vee x \in \Delta$). By Theorem 3.7, $\Gamma, \Delta \vdash M = M$ is provable for some M and M, M' are unique for given contexts and given M . By Theorem 3.17, $M' = \uparrow \uparrow^{len} M$. □

Corollary 3.20. (*aka streng*) *Suppose*

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma, x \vdash M = M' \text{ is provable for some } M' \\ &x \notin FV(M) \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma \vdash M = M \text{ is provable for some } M \text{ and} \\ &M' = \uparrow M \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.21. (*aka contr*) *Suppose*

$$\Gamma, x, x \vdash M = M' \text{ is provable for some } M'$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\Gamma, x \vdash M = M \text{ is provable for some } M \text{ and} \\ &M' = \uparrow \uparrow M \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Use Theorem 3.19 with $\Delta = x$ □

In fact, Corollary 2.9 also follows from Theorem 2.17.

Definition 3.22. Let $y \neq x$. Define substitution as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
[N/x]x &= N \\
[N/x]y &= y \\
[N/x]\lambda xM &= \lambda xM \\
[N/x]\lambda yM &= \lambda yM && (x \notin FV(M)) \\
[N/x]\lambda yM &= \lambda y[N/x]M && (x \in FV(M), y \notin FV(N)) \\
[N/x]\lambda yM &= \lambda z[N/x][z/y]M && (x \in FV(M), y \in FV(N)) \\
&&& \text{where } z = \text{fresh}(FV(M) \cup FV(N)) \\
[N/x](ML) &= ([N/x]M)[N/x]L
\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.23. $\text{count}(M)$ is the total number of lambdas in M

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{count}(x) &= 0 \\
\text{count}(\lambda xM) &= \text{count}(M) + 1 \\
\text{count}(MN) &= \text{count}(M) + \text{count}(N)
\end{aligned}$$

We will believe without proof that substitution is total function and

$$\text{count}([z/y]M) = \text{count}(M)$$

Fact 3.24.

- a) $[N/] \uparrow M = M$
- b) $[N/] \uparrow \uparrow \uparrow M = M$
- c) $[\uparrow N/](\binom{0}{1}) M = [N/] \uparrow M$
- d) $[0/] \uparrow \uparrow M = M$

These equalities are true in any cartesian closed category, which is easy to verify, but they have to be proved by tedious induction if we consider Table 4 as a definition. Equality 3.24(c) was used by de Bruijn in the first calculus of explicit substitutions ([3],[7]).

Theorem 3.25. (Main theorem) *The following rule is admissible*

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash M = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash [N/x]M = [N/]M}$$

Proof. Induction on $(count(M), length(M))$, ordered lexicographically. Suppose the rule is admissible for all M' such that $count(M') < count(M)$ or $count(M') = count(M) \wedge length(M') < length(M)$

Case 1. M is a variable y

Case 1.1. $y = x$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x]x = N$$

and the rule has the following trivial form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash x = \underline{0} \quad \Gamma \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}$$

where $M = \underline{0}$. Further,

$$[N/] \underline{0} = \mathbf{N} \quad (\text{FVar})$$

Case 1.2. $y \neq x$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x]y = y$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash y = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma \vdash y = [N/] M}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash y = \underline{m'} \end{array}}{\Gamma, x \vdash y = \underline{m' + 1}} \quad (\text{weakening})$$

therefore it must be $M = \underline{m' + 1}$, $[N/] M = \underline{m'}$
(for $\Gamma \vdash y = [N/] M$ to be provable).

Further,

$$[N/] M = m'$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} [N/] M &= \\ &= [N/] \underline{m' + 1} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \underline{m'} \quad (\text{RVar})$$

Case 2. M begins with lambda.

Case 2.1. M has the form $\lambda x M'$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda x M' = \lambda x M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda x M' = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x M' = [N/] M}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, x \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda x M' = \lambda M'} \quad (\text{lam})$$

where $M = \lambda M'$. By Corollary 3.21 (contr), if $\Gamma, x, x \vdash M' = M'$ is provable then $\Gamma, x \vdash M' = M''$ is provable for some M'' with the following property

$$M' = \uparrow \uparrow M'' \quad (*)$$

We can proof the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x \vdash M' = M'' \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x M' = \lambda M''} \quad (\text{lam})$$

Further,

$$[N/] M = \lambda M''$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} [N/] M &= \\ &= [N/] \lambda M' \\ &= [N/] \lambda \uparrow \uparrow M'' \quad (*) \\ &= \lambda [N/] \uparrow \uparrow M'' \quad (\text{Lambda}) \\ &= \lambda M'' \quad (3.24(b)) \end{aligned}$$

Case 2.2. M has the form $\lambda y M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \notin FV(M')$
The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y M' = \lambda y M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y M' = [N/] M}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = \lambda M'} \quad (lam)$$

where $M = \lambda M'$. We can proof the following

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash M' = \binom{0}{1} M'} \quad (3.15 \text{ perm})$$

By Corollary 3.20 (streng), if $\Gamma, y, x \vdash M' = \binom{0}{1} M'$ is provable then $\Gamma, y \vdash M' = M''$ is provable for some M'' with the following property

$$\binom{0}{1} M' = \uparrow M'' \quad (*)$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, y \vdash M' = M'' \end{array}}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y M' = \lambda M''} \quad (lam)$$

Further,

$$[N/] M = \lambda M''$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} [N/] M &= \\ &= [N/] \lambda M' \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \lambda [N/] \uparrow M' && \text{(Lambda)} \\
&= \lambda [\uparrow N/] \binom{0}{1} M' && \text{(3.24(c))} \\
&= \lambda [\uparrow N/] \uparrow M'' && (*) \\
&= \lambda M'' && \text{(3.24(a))}
\end{aligned}$$

Case 2.3. M has the form $\lambda y M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \in FV(M')$, $y \notin FV(N)$
The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y M' = \lambda y [N/x] M'$$

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y [N/x] M' = [N/] M}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = \lambda M'} \quad (lam)$$

where $M = \lambda M'$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rule is admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, y, x \vdash M' = \binom{0}{1} M' \quad \Gamma, y \vdash N = \uparrow N}{\Gamma, y \vdash [N/x] M' = [\uparrow N/] \binom{0}{1} M'}$$

We can prove the conclusion

$$\frac{\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, y, x \vdash M' = \binom{0}{1} M'} \quad (3.15 \text{ perm}) \quad \frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash N = N \end{array}}{\Gamma, y \vdash N = \uparrow N} \quad (3.18 \text{ weak})}{\Gamma, y \vdash [N/x] M' = [\uparrow N/] \binom{0}{1} M'} \quad (our \text{ rule})$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y \vdash [N/x] M' = [\uparrow N/] \binom{0}{1} M'}{\Gamma, y \vdash [N/x] M' = [N/] \uparrow M'} \quad (3.24(c))$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, y \vdash [N/x] M' = [N/] \uparrow M'}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda y [N/x] M' = \lambda [N/] \uparrow M'} \quad (lam)$$

Further,

$$\lambda [N/] \uparrow M' = [N/] M$$

because

$$\begin{aligned} [N/] M &= \\ &= [N/] \lambda M' \\ &= \lambda [N/] \uparrow M' \quad (\text{Lambda}) \end{aligned}$$

Case 2.4. M has the form $\lambda y M'$ where $x \neq y$, $x \in FV(M')$, $y \in FV(N)$
The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N/x] \lambda y M' = \lambda z [N/x] [z/y] M'$$

where $z \notin FV(M')$, $z \notin FV(N)$

(note that $z \neq x$ because $x \in FV(M')$ and $z \neq y$ because $y \in FV(N)$)

and the rule has the following form

$$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda z [N/x] [z/y] M' = [N/] M}$$

The unique proof of the first premise must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, x \vdash \lambda y M' = \lambda M'} \quad (\text{lam})$$

where $M = \lambda M'$. By the induction hypothesis, the following rules are admissible

$$\frac{\Gamma, x, z, y \vdash M' = \uparrow \uparrow M' \quad \Gamma, x, z \vdash z = \underline{0}}{\Gamma, x, z \vdash [z/y] M' = [\underline{0}/] \uparrow \uparrow M'} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, z, x \vdash [z/y] M' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} M' \quad \Gamma, z \vdash N = \uparrow N}{\Gamma, z \vdash [N/x] [z/y] M' = [\uparrow N/] \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} M'} \quad (2)$$

We can proof the conclusion

$$\begin{array}{c}
\vdots \\
\frac{\Gamma, x, y \vdash M' = M'}{\Gamma, x, z, y \vdash M' = \uparrow\uparrow M'} \text{ (3.17)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x, z \vdash z = \mathbf{0}}{\Gamma, x, z \vdash [z/y]M' = [\mathbf{0}/y] \uparrow\uparrow M'} \text{ (1)} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x, z \vdash [z/y]M' = [\mathbf{0}/y] \uparrow\uparrow M'}{\Gamma, x, z \vdash [z/y]M' = M'} \text{ (3.24(d))} \\
\frac{\Gamma, x, z \vdash [z/y]M' = M'}{\Gamma, z, x \vdash [z/y]M' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} M'} \text{ (3.15 perm)} \\
\frac{\Gamma \vdash \dot{N} = \mathbf{N}}{\Gamma, z \vdash N = \uparrow \mathbf{N}} \text{ (3.18 weak)} \\
\hline
\frac{\Gamma, z \vdash [N/x] [z/y]M' = [\uparrow \mathbf{N}/x] \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} M'}{\Gamma, z \vdash [N/x] [z/y]M' = [N/x] \uparrow\uparrow M'} \text{ (3.24(c))} \\
\frac{\Gamma, z \vdash [N/x] [z/y]M' = [N/x] \uparrow\uparrow M'}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda z [N/x] [z/y]M' = \lambda [N/x] \uparrow\uparrow M'} \text{ (lam)}
\end{array} \text{ (2)}$$

Further,

$$\lambda [N/x] \uparrow\uparrow M' = [N/x] M$$

because

$$\begin{aligned}
& [N/x] M = \\
& = [N/x] \lambda M' \\
& = \lambda [N/x] \uparrow\uparrow M' \quad (\text{Lambda})
\end{aligned}$$

Case 3. M has the form NL . Exercise.

Note that $\text{count}(N)$ may be equal to $\text{count}(NL)$, but $\text{length}(N) < \text{length}(NL)$

□

Tab. 5: Terms

$x, y, z, w ::= x \mid y \mid z \mid \dots$	(Variables)
$M, N ::= x \mid MN \mid \lambda x M$	(Terms)
$M, N ::= x \mid \underline{n} \mid MN \mid \lambda M$	(!!!De Bruijn Terms)

Tab. 6: Matching rules

$nil \vdash x = x$	
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash x = x}{\Gamma, y \vdash x = x} \quad (y \neq x)$	(weakening 2)
$\Gamma, x \vdash x = \underline{0}$	(axiom)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash x = \underline{n}}{\Gamma, y \vdash x = \underline{n+1}} \quad (y \neq x)$	(weakening)
$\frac{\Gamma \vdash M = M \quad \Gamma \vdash N = N}{\Gamma \vdash MN = MN}$	(app)
$\frac{\Gamma, x \vdash M = M}{\Gamma \vdash \lambda x M = \lambda M}$	(lam)

4 Coq

The file 99.v contains a proof of a theorem similar to Theorem 3.25, but with some differences. First of all, I consider de Bruijn terms with variable names ([5]) and I add the following new matching rules

$$nil \vdash x = x \quad (\text{where } nil \text{ is the empty context})$$

and “weakening 2”

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash x = x}{\Gamma, y \vdash x = x} \quad (y \neq x)$$

We can prove $\Gamma \vdash x = x$ iff $x \notin \Gamma$

Example 4.1.

$$\frac{y \vdash y = \underline{0} \quad \frac{nil \vdash x = x}{y \vdash x} \text{ (weakening 2)}}{y \vdash yx = \underline{0}x} \text{ (app)}$$

Theorem 4.2. $\Gamma \vdash M = M$ is provable for a unique M and the proof is unique (Γ and M are arbitrary).

In fact, I don't use matching rules in 99.v at all, but define a function "transfer" with the following property

$$\text{transfer } \Gamma M = M \text{ iff } \Gamma \vdash M = M \text{ is provable}$$

Further, I use parallel substitution with the following essential properties

$$\begin{aligned} [N_1/x_1 \dots N_k/x_k, N/x]x &= N \\ [N_1/x_1 \dots N_k/x_k, N/y]x &= [N_1/x_1 \dots N_k/x_k]x \quad (x \neq y) \\ []x &= x \end{aligned}$$

and the corresponding "De Bruijn's parallel substitution"

$$\begin{aligned} [N_1/ \dots N_k/, N/] \underline{0} &= N \\ [N_1/ \dots N_k/, N/] \underline{n+1} &= [N_1/ \dots N_k/] \underline{n} \\ [] \underline{n} &= \underline{n} \\ [N_1/ \dots N_k/] x &= x \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. *Suppose*

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma \vdash N_1 &= N_1 \\ &\dots \\ \Gamma \vdash N_k &= N_k \\ \Gamma, x_1 \dots x_k \vdash M &= M \end{aligned}$$

and all the variables $x_1 \dots x_k$ are pairwise distinct. Then

$$\Gamma \vdash [N_1/x_1 \dots N_k/x_k] M = [N_1/ \dots N_k/] M$$

Proof. (sketch) Instead of $\binom{0}{1}$ we need a more general function *rot*

$$\text{rot } n \underline{0} = \underline{n}$$

$$\text{rot } n \underline{1} = \underline{0}$$

$$\text{rot } n \underline{2} = \underline{1}$$

...

$$\text{rot } n \underline{n} = \underline{n-1}$$

$$\text{rot } n \underline{k + (n+1)} = \underline{k + (n+1)}$$

For example,

$$\text{rot } 2 \underline{0} = \underline{2}$$

$$\text{rot } 2 \underline{1} = \underline{0}$$

$$\text{rot } 2 \underline{2} = \underline{1}$$

$$\text{rot } 2 \underline{k+3} = \underline{k+3}$$

Suppose that

$$z \neq x, z \neq y, z \notin FV(N_1), z \notin FV(N_2)$$

The substitution is calculated as follows

$$[N_1/x, N_2/y] \lambda z M' = \lambda z [N_1/x, N_2/y] M'$$

The unique proof of $\Gamma, x, y \vdash \lambda z M' = M$ must be of the form

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y, z \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, x, y \vdash \lambda z M' = \lambda M'} \quad (\text{lam})$$

We can prove

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma, x, y, z \vdash M' = M' \end{array}}{\Gamma, z, x, y \vdash M' = \text{rot } 2 M'} \quad (\text{some Lemma})$$

Further, we have the proofs

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash N_1 = \mathbf{N}_1 \end{array}}{\Gamma, z \vdash N_1 = \uparrow \mathbf{N}_1} \quad (weak)$$

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \vdots \\ \Gamma \vdash N_2 = \mathbf{N}_2 \end{array}}{\Gamma, z \vdash N_2 = \uparrow \mathbf{N}_2} \quad (weak)$$

By the induction hypothesis, we can prove

$$\Gamma, z \vdash [N_1/x, N_2/y] M' = [\uparrow \mathbf{N}_1/, \uparrow \mathbf{N}_2/] rot 2 M'$$

Then we use the fact

$$[\uparrow \mathbf{N}_1/, \uparrow \mathbf{N}_2/] rot 2 M' = [\mathbf{N}_1/, \mathbf{N}_2/] \uparrow M'$$

□

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